

Role of Camerawoman in the Process of Television News Coverage at the Military Judicial Proceedings I/02 Medan

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ABSTRACT

Information becomes very important in people's lives. It has been marked by the emergence of information society including in Indonesia. Factors contributing to the creation of the society are the emergence of new technologies, news media, and news audiences. Audiovisual or television technology that may at this time has become a favorite of Indonesian society as a medium that allows to spread information without any space and time limits. The media therefore seeks to fulfill the demands of the community by presenting information quickly, but still pay attention to the principles and code of ethics that are accurate, actual and factual. In the making of news programs, various elements are required to be delivered and distributed to the wider community. Some key elements that make a news program can serve are producers, coverage coordinators, reporters, cameraman and editors. In the implementation of the producer is someone who is harvesting the team and is responsible for the news that aired. A coverage coordinator is a person who is looking for information according to the producer's direction to give directions to the reporter and the field cameraman. A Reporter is someone who is tasked with searching for data. Cameraman is a person responsible for visual/image recording as the raw material of the news-making at the moment of coverage. And editors are tasked to make the materials obtained from the field become an impression that is ready to show. Cameraman/It has a very important role in audiovisual media. Because in every news, to be served contains several elements that are information, audio/sound and video/images. Without any visuals/images that support audio/sound from the information

obtained, the given dish has less response from the audience. How an audio/sound and video/image is coupled with the best possible to present a more detailed information for the audience. For audio/sound can be manipulated or inserted when it is entered in the Space editor by the team but not for a picture of events that occur.

Keywords: *Cameraman, Camerawoman, Military Judicial Proceedings*

INTRODUCTION

Humans are social beings who cannot live alone. Therefore, man must communicate with other human beings in order to survive. Communication is a process of conveying information from one human to another. Communication serves to inform, educate, entertain and influence. Communication consists of various, among others, intrapersonal communication, interpersonal communication, Mass communication, etc.

The types of mass media that are present in our lives today include newspapers, magazines, television, radio, movies, and the Internet. But of all the media of the communication, television has the greatest influence in human life. Televisions can quickly convey information from both close and long distances.

Once the importance of an image makes the cameraman can be said to be the spearhead in any of the coverage. Then every cameraman should always be ready to standby wherever he is. And the cameraman should always know what news he will

capture by discussing with the reporter and the latest news updates during the office. At a time when there was news that had to be quickly broadcast a cameraman should be able to take pictures cut to cut and sequential so that the editor did not need a long time to edit the image. Especially with the rise of television in Indonesia makes the competition increasingly tight to deliver the latest news. Here the cameraman should be able to compete for a strategic place so that the resulting image is clearly visible and good at the location of the coverage.

The cameraman must be able to and agile using a tool used to make the image look bright, focused and not shake. A cameraman must also be able to put the objects that will be displayed in the picture in a well-seen position or can be said with the composition accordingly. There are several roles that the cameraman can do. Some of the roles that can be done by the cameraman are as a director (PD) program, coordinator of the coverage on-air, on-air cameraman, studio cameraman and cameraman.

One of the problems that often occur is the lack of the coverage of military judicial proceedings through television media, especially in the city of Medan, therefore it is important and useful to the knowledge of the public to the course of the proceedings of the Ministry of Government violations and outside the service of the Indonesian Armed Forces (TNI) in the military judicial environment in addition, TNI is also limited by laws and military regulations so that all actions that are also based on applicable laws and regulations. The implementation of duties and obligations are heavy and special, the TNI is educated and trained to obey the commandments or the ruling without denying and implement them appropriately.

The existence of military judiciary is necessary considering that the TNI is also an ordinary social human that does not escape the various mistakes that have been made in everyday life both during office and outside the service. The military judiciary is

an executive of judicial power in the armed forces to enforce law and justice by observing the interests of the State security defense. (Al Araf, et. Al, 2007) Considered in terms of law, military members have the same position as the ordinary community members, meaning that as citizens, they apply all applicable legal provisions, both criminal, civil, criminal and civil events (Moch. Faisal Salam, 1994). The difference is seen only because of the burden of liabilities that are more mandated by the State to the TNI than ordinary people in terms of state defense.

METHOD

This research is a normative juridical study, with a of approach, a conceptual approach, used by researchers to analyse the role of cameraman in news coverage of the application of criminal penalties against the TNI members who were examined and tried in the Military Court I/02 Medan. The concept approach was used by researchers to analyse the implementation of the proceedings against members/soldiers who committed criminal acts.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

News Coverage

News coverage, in this case constitutes the coverage of criminal news as well as violations of the law of military discipline in the sphere of military justice I/02 in Medan, which means the process of collecting data conducted by journalists (Camerans/TI, reporters and journalists), this process is a direct monitoring and recording of events that occur or interviews with a number of interviewees.

Media Television

Watching television is already a community consumption nowadays. No matter in the village or in the city. No matter the top or middle and bottom. Now they make television as a basic necessity. Television with the news display has become a part of life. With its immediaty nature, television media is able to bring the

events and places of the scene with the audience (Askurifai Baksin, 2006).

Television is the most excellent media among other communication media today. The reality and information on an event can be packaged so interestingly to be brought to the viewer. The messages delivered are not only heard but can be seen through a glass screen with a view of moving images. With the advantages that television has compared to other media, it certainly brings a greater impact to the audience. The events are presented to influence the way of thinking, lifestyle, behaviour and so on.

In the book of four Windu TVRI also mentioned that the television media underwent a gradual change in technology. First generation television is a black and white television. Here the reflectivity rays after passing through the lens system will form a black and white projection image. This projection image is instantly converted into a black and white projection image signal. So be the black and white television broadcast in Indonesia we know in the 60-an. In subsequent developments, the reflective rays after being passed by the lens system, channeled also a prism/dichroic so that the formed three basic colors, namely red (red), green (green), and blue (blue) that formed a color projection image (colour). Three projection images are red, green and blue, which will also result in a colored projection image on the television screen. Second-generation television is color television (Askurifai Baksin, 2006).

Television News

A television must have a news show program that is packaged in such a way as to attract the attention of the audience. The contents of the news between television stations and others compete with each other to deliver more actual and reliable impressions.

The news is generally categorized into three parts, namely (Dedy Iskandar Muda, 2005):

1. Hard News or heavy news is news about important events for people both as individuals, groups, and organizations.
2. Soft News or light news is often also called with the feature of news that is not related to actuality but has an appeal for audience audiences.
3. Investigative reports, also known as investigation reports (investigation), are exclusive types of news. The data cannot be obtained on the surface, but it should be done based on the synchronize. So the presentation of this kind of news takes a long time and will certainly spend the energy of the Reporternya.

Military Judiciary

The military judiciary is one of the judicial institutions under the Supreme Court which has a Yustisiabale (judge's authority) in which the culprit is TNI soldiers. Since July 2004 based on the decree of the President of Indonesia No. 56 year 2004 has been carried out the transfer of the organization in the military Justice environment from the TNI MABES to the Supreme Court of Indonesia. This is the realization of Law No. 4 of 2004 on judicial authority.

In law No. 4 of 2004 Jo. Law No. 48 year 2009 of judicial authority, article 10 paragraph (1) affirmed that judicial authority is carried out by a Supreme Court and the body under it. Further in Article 13 paragraph (1) It is affirmed that the Organization, administration and financial of the Supreme Court and the judicial body under it shall be one roof of the Supreme Court. Thus the military Tribunal with all its limitations and deficiencies must be able to carry out military judicial duties in line with other judiciary.

The military judiciary is authorised by law as a special judicial that examines and prosecute crimes committed by an organization-organised population in the Indonesian National armed Forces, specifically established to carry out state

duties in conducting state defense subjugated and enforced by military law.

Criminal acts committed by each member of the Indonesian National Army will be in the process in accordance with the provisions of the applicable criminal law, that is processed in accordance with the provisions of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia number 34 year 2004 about the Indonesian National Army (TNI), the attitude of members of the Indonesian National Army is contrary to the duty of the Indonesian National Army as stipulated in article 7 paragraph (1) of the Law 2004 34 , maintain the integrity of the territory of the unitary Republic of Indonesia based on the Pancasila and the Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia year 1945, and protect all nations and all the blood of Indonesia from threats and disruption to the integrity of the nation and state ".

There is no denying that a military member should be a good citizen, even supposedly the best. In order to implement the duties charged to the shoulder, then in addition to being a good citizen he must have the ability and traits that are patriotic, knight, steadfast in carrying out his legal obligations in the circumstances however, uphold the attitude of the soldiers and have a sense of discipline and personality that is expected to be a role model for the surrounding community, as well as a focus of hope for the Nation and Dignity (Sandrasta , 2015).

Some time ago the military judiciary was highlighted about the military judiciary not open or not transparent and many public complaints of justice seekers addressed to the Ministry of Justice because of the low quality of the ruling judge in prosecute a case. To get out of this situation, the duties of the judges and their special roles and journalists of Kamerawati in realizing a clean and transparent judicial and manifesting the mission of Justice.

The Military tribunal has the authority to inspect and prosecute TNI soldiers who commit criminal acts where the state is in peace or in a state of danger

(civil emergency, martial law and war emergency). This means even though the state of the Republic of law must remain enforced, under any circumstances both peaceful and in the condition of war and whoever the culprit is both civil and military to be tried according to the prevailing regulations for the creation of justice, peace, tranquility and legal certainty in society, as is the law Adagium "Fiat Justitia ruat coelum" which means even though the sky collapsed law should remain enforced.

Cameraman/Camerawoman Concept

The profesionalism of a television cameraman in the shooting was assessed when the image of his work was examined before being edited in an editing space. The basic knowledge of absolute image editing techniques must be noticed by the cameraman. The understanding of editing techniques is crucial for the cameraman as a basis for him to take pictures. Many opinions say one must first learn to edit pictures before he works as a cameraman (Morissan, M. A, 1990).

According to the author can be concluded that in the process of news coverage in the TV news show program The most important is a cameraman must be as follows:

1. Have motivation from every picture taken so it can be received by the audience
2. The composition of the placement of an image object must be correct 3.
3. The shooting angle must be artistic value so that the preview is not saturated.

However, according to the author in the news coverage in the military judicial environment I/02 Medan is not as easy as imagined because in the Conference on the TNI (Indonesian National Armed Forces) has a Juklak (instruction and implementing) and must comply with the SOP (standard Opersional procedure), and also the news coverage in the military judiciary is not the same as the news coverage at the general judiciary, and usually the military judiciary is very strict on the rules applied, because it

could affect the name of both the TNI and the TNI who faced at the conference.

CONCLUSION

In law Number 31 year 1997 concerning Military Court governs the provisions of the Organization and the workmanship of the military court in prosecute the TNI members who are guilty of committing criminal acts and disciplinary violations, therefore, so that against the people of the TNI members should be notified of the identity as detailed as possible through social and electronic

Participation of journalists or cameraman/it in the conference coverage in the military judiciary I/02 Medan is needed, so that the public knows the ordinances of the proceedings against the people of the TNI who commit the criminal act in the jurisdiction of the Kodam I/BB, although the process of events in the military court was the same with the process of the event in the General Court, but the confidentiality of the TNI soldiers who commit criminal acts or violations of law of military discipline, can not simply be exposed or covered as in the general judicial environment, although the principle of the trial "the Council is declared open and open to the public", but we see the reality in the field of society reluctant and feel afraid to come see the course of the military justice process, moreover there are some conditions must leave an identity card (KTP) If you want to follow the course The application of information technology in the notification and personnel services in the military Justice environment became a strategic step for journalists or cameraman/TI in the coverage of criminal news against the ARMY members of the Military Court I/02 Medan, therefore against cameraman and Kamerawati as the leading guard in the news coverage also encouraged the bureaucracy reform that is being run by the government. The focus that you want to achieve from implementing this information

technology is to improve the quality of personnel service to its customers.

REFERENCES

1. Al Araf, dkk, 2007, Reformasi Peradilan Militer di Indonesia, Jakarta: Imparsial.
2. Baksin, Askurifai. 2006. *Jurnalistik Televisi Teori dan Praktik*, Bandung, PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
3. Deddy Iskandar. 2005. *Jurnalistik Televisi: Menjadi Reporter Profesional*. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
4. Effendy, Onong Uchjana.1990. *TV Siaran Teori dan Praktek*. Bandung: Mandar Maju.
5. Morissan, M.A. 2008. *Manajemen Media Penyiaran*, Jakarta, Kencana Muda.
6. Moch. Faisal Salam, 1994, *Peradilan Militer Indonesia*, Bandung: Mandar Maju.
7. Sandrasta, 2015, *Tugas dan Fungsi Prajurit Tentara Nasional Indonesia*, Jakarta, CV.Jaya Sakti.
8. Wahyudi, JB. 1986. *Media Komunikasi Massa Televisi*. Bandung, PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
9. Republic of Indonesia, Constitution year 1945.
10. Republic of Indonesia, Law number 39 Year 1947 about the code of Military criminal law.
11. Republic of Indonesia, Law number 31 Year 1997 on Military Court (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia 1997 number 84, Addition of State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia number 3713).
12. Republic of Indonesia, Act No. 48 year 2009 on Judicial Authority (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia 2009 Number 157, Supplement to State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia number 5076).
13. Republic of Indonesia, law number 25 of 2014 about the Law of Military Discipline (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia 2014 No. 257, Supplement to State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia number 5591).

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